

SEVERAL TIERS THAT CAN ASSIST IN ASSESSING THE TRAINING PROGRAMMS.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14778556>

Abstract: Today's world everybody is living in active life that want to change their life in good side. As Ralph Marston mentioned "What you do today can improve all your tomorrows." It means people should try to create the things and methods which ease their life and develop it in the future. Don Kirkpatrick also did such a necessary creation in evaluating trainings that can help to show results and development of training. Even this method consists of just four steps: Reaction, Learning, Behavior and Result it really works effectively if we do it in order to obtain goals which are expected before a project.

Key words: Methods, reaction ,change behaviour, project, conducting trainings

Introduction.

By evaluating training programs at each of these four levels, organizations can gain a comprehensive understanding of the effectiveness of their training initiatives and make informed decisions about future training investments. The Four Levels of Training Evaluation, also known as the Kirkpatrick Model, are a widely used framework for evaluating the effectiveness of training programs.

Context of the Program:

Time by time the knowledge of world is updated and improving as Ravinder Tulsiani mentioned "Training sessions are vital to the learning process but they are only one step in the learning process and this should never be forgotten" To clarify this point of view I can say there are many innovations and changes in every sphere because of training programs which leads to great results . I have decided to make my own evaluation plan for medical trainees who are taught in the training. Mainly, the training involves medical knowledge and skills, communication rules, policies and procedures, time management and hands on experience. After getting such knowledge, nurses have great opportunity to improve their experience on their field because every lecture is conducted face to face. Moreover, there is organized conferences and meetings with medical celebrities and productive presentations held by trainers. As it is unimaginable medicine without practice trainees can do some practice during their courses.

Purpose of evaluation

As it stated above nursing sphere is considered one of the developing spheres in the world. In order to stay up-to-date knowledge, nurses must participate such trainings and they have to be evaluated. The main aim of the evaluation process is to test participants how much they acquire from given information and how they use this knowledge when they come back to their job. Again there is one question whether intended goals are achieved from the training which are put before organizing it.

When evaluating training programs, it's important to consider the following key aspects:

1. Objectives: Clearly define the objectives of the training program. What specific knowledge, skills, or behaviors are expected to be developed or improved as a result of the training?
2. Data Collection: Use a variety of methods to collect data at each level of the Kirkpatrick Model. This can include surveys, interviews, pre and post-training assessments, performance evaluations, observations, and organizational metrics.
3. Relevance: Assess the relevance of the training content to the participants' roles and the organization's needs. Determine if the training is aligned with current best practices and industry standards.
4. Participant Engagement: Evaluate the level of participant engagement during the training. Consider factors such as participation rates, interaction with the material, and overall enthusiasm for the training content.
5. Learning Outcomes: Measure the knowledge, skills, and attitudes gained by participants as a result of the training. Look for evidence of increased competence and confidence in applying new knowledge.

6. Application of Learning: Assess whether participants are applying what they learned in their work environment. Look for changes in behavior, performance improvements, and the integration of new skills into daily tasks.

1.Reaction

Reaction is attitude towards training which is conducted to trainees. This step is considered one of the most important processes that without good reaction ,in terms of work explained, can not be expected good results and desire to implement it. There are two types of reaction they are positive and negative. Each has its influence on learning and behavior for instance it is said on the article that positive reaction is very important to develop a project as a successful project in the future .However, negative reaction leads to prevent from learning if a person does not have a positive attitude towards the training it means he has not got motivation to start a project . So while conducting a trainings instructors should take participants needs into account without thinking only giving new information . In order to check participants reaction there are so many ways whether they get interested in that project or not. First of all, ranking the the quality of the training by several methods : people should tick one of the possible answers like excellent ,good , poor by answering such questionnaires session is conducted alive and interesting or there is an opportunity to use communicative skills ,that is an friendly and helpful manner and so on. Another method, giving full feedback who do not like short reactions towards a project that is also good way to collect information while evaluating client's reaction. When I worked as a tutor in my private school I used the first method to clarify my students attitude to my classes in case I know my weak points and change them in the future. I think it was workable. As reaction is based on motivation and people needs and interest that is very important level while we are working with our costumers. In every sphere we can see costumers their need should be at the top of the stages.

2. Learning

Every trainee should put an aim before themselves :

What knowledge I learnt?

What skills I improved?

How I could change behavior?

One can find answer those questions in learning process. So it is very crucial to measure learning because it is said that no behavior change occurs as long as specific knowledge is gained related to a project. When we evaluate participant's learning stage we use different methods in order to collect information about what customers could get from the project. One of the popular methods is taking pretests at the beginning of the training and to compare the results of learning skills instructors should take such a test at the end of the project. Through this way it can be seen clearly improvement in learning and behavior. On consequences of such testing, it is seen not only results of participants but also effectiveness of instructors too. So in order to achieve positive changes in behavior and show exact results measuring leaning process is vital.

3. Behaviour

The third level in Kirkpatrick's model is behavior. This level is considered by far more complicated than other two levels. As after having a positive reaction to the project and having gained some knowledge in terms of that work the following step will be to implement this change in behavior When that person come back to the job. The most difficult side of that is it takes a lot of time to measure whether there is behavior change or not. To find out an answer to this question and collect some information it had better to use a survey or interview people who knows you well. It will be better if a supervisor is conducting an interview because they know their costumers attitudes before the training and they can easily analyze what improvements are there after the training. For instance we can see in exhibit 6.1 according to Kirkpatrick's model there are some questionnaires for evaluating behavior .

4. Result

The last process is evaluating the result. Finding the answers to those questions given at the beginning of the project what are obtained through the project. The best way of evaluating the result is to take

measurement both before and after a project this will be easier comparing to first three levels because a participant of a training already knows how is her reaction to a project, what knowledge she has gained and what changes she feels in her behavior after three main evolution it can be obvious what results she achieved.

Summary

As I stated above D. Kirkpatrick did his best in creating four level of evaluation model which impacts on training programs. To clarify my point of view, reaction is desire that unwillingly a person attitudes towards a trainings it leads getting nothing through it. Without knowing anything participants can not do positive changes in their life. If a person is not able to change his behavior it means the training was useless. So in order to show the effectiveness of a training trainees should follow three of models which is clearly explained and created by D. Kirkpatrick.

References

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